

Leveraging ALOS-2 PALSAR-2 for mapping built-up areas and assessing their vertical component

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Abstract— Built-up areas extraction and characterization from remote sensing images is essential for monitoring urbanization and the associated challenges. This work presents a novel integrated classification framework building on the Symbolic Machine Learning classifier and fully polarimetric PALSAR-2 to derive both the extent and vertical components of built-up areas from the same scene. It also explores the complementarity between ascending and descending orbits of PALSAR-2 for built-up areas detection. The experimental results in Chicago and Tokyo cities with different landscape and characteristics of built-up areas demonstrate that the proposed generic method can achieve three main challenges of urban remote sensing: i) enabling automated delineation of built-up areas at a spatial resolution of 5 meters with a balanced accuracy of 85% using globally available low resolution training data, ii) assessing the density of building height class with a RMSE of 0.25, 0.034, and 0.032 for the low-rise, mid-rise, and high-rise building density class, respectively and iii) dealing with the scattering components of buildings with different orientation angles by combining data from ascending and descending orbits for enhanced mapping of built-up areas.

Index terms—ALOS-2, PALSAR-2, PolSAR, Symbolic Machine Learning, Built-up areas, vertical component

I. INTRODUCTION

Urban areas are expanding over the world. Evidence shows that the population living in cities, has more than doubled over the last 40 years, going from 1.5 billion inhabitants in 1975 to 3.5 billion in 2015. It is projected to reach 5 billion and almost 55% of the world population by 2050 [1]. In light of the growing population and the associated challenges (i.e. climate change, inequality, economic development), the future that awaits urban areas is intricate, calling for a framework such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) to provide a roadmap for more balanced and equitable urban development [2]. In response to

the increasing urban population and higher demand for land and infrastructure, cities adopt different urban expansion strategies usually characterized by an interplay between horizontal growth with addition of new settlements and vertical development (promoting concentration of population and economic activity in central locations) [3]. Considering the role that growth of urban areas plays on the surrounding environment and the related socio-economic impacts, constant monitoring of urban environments and their characteristics is needed as a key for a sustainable urban development and for smart urban planning. In that regard, Earth Observation is recognized by the United Nations and global stakeholders as an important data source for mapping anthropogenic areas and the provision of essential evidence on the characteristic of urban areas for achieving the SDGs targets, in particular those related to Goal 11 on Sustainable Cities and Communities.

Mapping of the built-up environment can be achieved with different types of sensors by analysing surface reflectance [4] of building material or its thermal [5] or microwave properties [6] and nightlight emissions [7]. Compared to the horizontal information, the vertical component reflects urban compactness and can be extracted through optical stereo photogrammetry, airborne light detection and ranging and analysis of Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR). The large majority of works in remote sensing tackle either the horizontal or the vertical component of the built-up environment. This is related either to the limited capabilities of one type of sensor alone to provide information on both components or to the limitations of the adopted image analysis approaches that are usually tailored for the classification of either 2D or the 3D features of urban areas. Zhang et al. (2017) [8] detected horizontal and vertical urban characteristics and their growth using Landsat imagery (30 m). However, their exploratory method for detecting mid

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and tall rise buildings requires post-classified land-cover maps and expert-interpreted sample data limiting the replicability of the approach and its application to large areas. Recently [9], mapped building footprint, height, and volume at a continental scale and at 1 km² resolution by combining built-up areas extent as assessed in the Global Urban Footprint (GUF) [10] with backscatter intensity from SAR for estimating building height. [11] proposed an approach to extract non-building and building objects and assess building heights automatically using high-resolution (2 m) multi-view ZY-3 satellite imagery. To do so, two independent methods were developed: one for the extraction of buildings using object-based image analysis and one for the estimating building height through semi-global matching of multi-view images. The use of time-series multi-view ZY-3 high-resolution satellite images was further investigated in [12] for automatically monitoring newly constructed building areas. A joint use of planar-vertical features and the inclusion of multi-temporal images allowed deriving horizontal and vertical spatiotemporal information on newly constructed built-up areas. However, due to the limitations of the ZY-3 data acquisition ability, it may not be easy to apply proposed methods for large scale urban mapping with a single sensor mainly because of cloud contamination and limited swath.

In [13] combined optical and SAR data were used and classified differently to classify landcover and characterize urban forms including their vertical components in the city of Shanghai. In particular, the authors exploited fully polarimetric Advanced Land Observing Satellite-2 Phased Array type L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar-2 (ALOS-2 PALSAR-2). Polarimetric capabilities of SAR data were investigated for land cover mapping in urban areas, where the use of dual polarization proved superior to single polarization [14]. The fully polarimetric SAR (PolSAR) data holds even more promise for built-up areas detection and characterization thanks to the joint development of high-resolution and multi-polarization technologies. Compared with single and dual-polarization SAR data, PolSAR can provide even better descriptions of land cover from observations at orthogonal polarizations [15]. This represents an interesting information source for built-up areas extraction and identification. [16] reviewed different works on built-up areas mapping from PolSAR data. The commonality between the methods developed in that domain is the exploitation of decomposition theorems to feed into classification frameworks ranging from decision trees to mixture models to deep

learning [17] and to novel PolSAR built-up areas index composed by considering scattering mechanisms from built-up structures [16]. These state of the art methods represent interesting methodological directions for exploiting the potential of PolSAR data, in particular for extracting the horizontal component of urban areas. However they are not suitable for assessing the vertical component which is essential for a comprehensive characterization of urban areas. [18] exploited fine resolution PolSAR data to describe changes due to building density and heights through a combination of decomposition measures derived from two Radarsat-2 images. The approach showed the effectiveness of polarimetric features at the superpixel level to describe 2D and 3D. However it did not address the issue of estimating building heights.

In this paper we propose to address built-up areas extraction and characterization through these different techniques, but with additional constraints, which have not been dealt with in the literature up to now: i) the requirement for an automated classification method potentially scalable to global data scenarios by using already available learning set data, ii) the exploitation of PolSAR scattering mechanisms for deriving both the horizontal and vertical characteristics of built-up areas while assessing the added-value of ascending-descending orbit combination.

To do so, we leverage the exclusive high-resolution and fully polarimetric PALSAR-2 and develop an integrated classification framework building on the Symbolic Machine Learning (SML) classifier to derive both the extent and the vertical components of built-up areas from the same scene. The SML is a generic classification framework developed by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission [19] and used as a core technology for solving global or very large automatic image data classification scenarios by using global categorical data as learning set even if available at lower resolution respect to the classified image data. The interscale learning paradigm was introduced in [20] [21] [22] and successfully demonstrated in mapping built-up areas at the European and global scales from a variety of sensors: very high resolution optical satellite data [23], Landsat imagery [24] and more recently Sentinel-1 GRD [25] and Sentinel -2 data [26], [27]. The flexibility of the SML enables the integration of radiometric, textural and morphological features for improving the classification outputs. Recent works have demonstrated the potential for

methodological adaptations of the SML to include information on interferometric coherence and backscatter intensity change to extract built-up areas from Sentinel-1 SAR data [28]. The current study goes one step further by evaluating the capacity of the classifier to incorporate polarimetric data derived from PALSAR-2 for mapping the built-up areas and their vertical component. The novelty of this work is two-fold:

- It proposes a generic method with a dual scope aiming at extracting built-up areas from PALSAR-2 data and assessing their vertical components using the same classifier;
- It explores the complementarity between ascending and descending orbits of PALSAR-2 for built-up areas detection.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A. Study sites:

Two sites have been selected for the experiments covering the cities of Chicago and Tokyo. Both study areas cover a surface of 3,500 km² approximately.

In 2015, Chicago urban centre had an average population density of 1,770 inhabitants/km² and a built-up per capita of 415 m² per inhabitant according to the Urban Centres Database of the Global Human Settlement Layer [29]. In Tokyo the average population density was 3.5 times more than in Chicago with 6,211 inhabitants/km² while the built-up per capita was 3.7 times less with 111 m² per inhabitant. The mean elevation of terrain in the urban centres of Chicago and Tokyo are 204 m and 38 m respectively.

Both cities are characterized by a strong heterogeneity of human settlements with low-rise buildings in the urban neighbourhood with a dominance of residential housing. Whereas the central business districts are characterized by a dominance of high-rise buildings.

The main land cover types in Chicago are built-up areas surrounded by forest, herbaceous vegetation, cropland and permanent water bodies and in Tokyo we encounter also a diversity of land cover with dense built-up areas surrounded by forest, cropland and permanent waterbodies. In Chicago, the city's mapping system identifies about 20,800 unique city blocks surrounded typically by four streets in a rectangular pattern². A city block is primarily a plot of

land defined all around by a multitude of planned and unplanned road and streets and defined by an edge and an interior where the edge is directly connected with the street and is understood as the public realm and the interior is a private zone [30]. The city block is the fundamental element of physical structure of urban areas. In Tokyo, the irregular arrangements of neighbourhoods and diversity in block forms, mainly due to the landform, have produced a strikingly unique urban fabric which makes it difficult to count the individual blocks. The business district alone has 11 city blocks.

Fig. 1. Study sites and footprints of the available ALOS-2 PALSAR-2 scenes

² <https://www.dnainfo.com/chicago/20170106/downtown/number-of-blocks-in-chicago/>

B. PALSAR-2 data and preprocessing:

The L-band (1.2 GHz, 24 cm) PALSAR-2 data for the two sites were provided as SLC L1.1 data by the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA). One scene was acquired for Chicago in ascending mode on 12/05/2015, which is the default orbit for global acquisition. In the case of Tokyo, two scenes were made available, including one in ascending mode acquired on 06/08/2019 and one in descending mode acquired on 16/07/2019 (Fig. 1 and TABLE I).

The descending mode is principally limited to low data-rate (120 Mbps) ScanSAR observations at HH polarization. However, for Japan, the default sensor observations modes are defined individually allowing the acquisition of data with fine beam mode (at the highest spatial resolution) and at all four polarizations. The availability of the two scenes with similar characteristics but obtained from two different ascending and descending paths represents an opportunity to assess the performance of the classification with respect to the acquisition orbit.

TABLE I. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE THREE PALSAR-2 SCENES

	<i>Tokyo1</i>	<i>Tokyo2</i>	<i>Chicago</i>
Acquisition data	16/07/2019	06/08/2019	12/05/2015
Orbit	descending	ascending	ascending
Spatial coverage	3,545.91 km ²	3,571.79 km ²	3,530.83 km ²
Central coordinates (m)	139.822, 35.847	139.805, 35.848	-87.368, 41.52
Pixel spacing:			
Slant Range		5.1 m	
Pixel spacing:			
Azimuth Range		4.3 m	
Incidence angle	27.79°	27.80°	27.80°
Off-nadir angle		25°	
Polarizations	HH-HV-VV-VH		

The pre-processing of the complex data consisted in radiometric calibration on the four polarization channels HH, HV, VH, and VV followed by the transfer of the Sinclair scatter matrix to coherence matrix T3. To reduce the inherent speckle, we applied a polarimetric speckle filter based on incoherent averaging of the coherence matrix. The refined Lee Filter with a window size of 5x5 was used without any additional multilooking to avoid degrading the spatial resolution of the images [31].

Polarimetric scattering power decomposition parameters have shown to be suitable, low-level features, for the classification of built-up areas [32]. Several methods are available in the literature; however most of them show limitations for the classification of built-up areas because of the problems

related to orientation of targets with respect to the radar line of sight. In general, many man-made targets with dominant double-bounce scattering, such as buildings aligned along radar flight direction (i.e. orthogonal buildings), can be extracted effectively in the polarimetric dimension. However, when the buildings are oriented away from the radar line of sight (i.e. obliquely oriented buildings), a significant cross-polarized component is produced, which can lead to confusion with vegetation [17]. To address this issue, [33] proposed an improved decomposition schema based on the deorientation theory [34]. This consists in applying a rotation of the coherency matrix to minimize the cross-polarized component and subsequently, the four-component scattering power decomposition. This new improved decomposition has the potential to partially address the problem of deoriented targets and therefore has been adopted in this study. For each PALSAR-2 scene, a rotated coherency matrix $T(\theta)$ (θ is the rotation angle) was created, then four images were generated from the rotated coherency matrix corresponding to four scattering components of the image pixel area: surface scattering (P_s), double-bounce scattering (P_d), volume scattering (P_v), and helix scattering (P_c). The resulting four scattering components represent the low level features to be used as input to the classification process.

Finally, we performed terrain correction of the generated bands using the SRTM 1 Digital Elevation Model and sampled the outputs to a spatial resolution of 5 meters.

C. Overview of the SML

The SML is a statistical classification framework developed at the JRC. The SML method is based on the concept of the empirical multidimensional histogram where statistical associations among class labels and sequences of low-level features derived from the input imagery are assessed. A normalized measure of association scores these sequences according to their conditional frequency of occurrence inside and outside the target class labels as observed during the training. The analysis of the cumulative distribution of the estimated scores is used at the end in their reclassification. The classification schema includes two steps:

1. Data reduction of the input bands or low-level features to their symbolic representation.
2. Evaluation of the *association* between the unique data-sequences X (input features) and

the learning set Y (known class abstraction derived from a learning set).

In the application proposed here, the data-abstraction association is evaluated by a confidence measure called Evidence-Based Normalized Differential Index (ENDI) which is statistical confidence measure produced in the continuous $[-1, 1]$ range. The ENDI confidence measure Φ of data instances X provided the Y^+ positive and negative Y^- data instances from the learning set is defined as follows:

$$\Phi(X|Y^+, Y^-) = \frac{f^+ - f^-}{f^+ + f^-} \quad (1)$$

where f^+ and f^- are the frequencies of the joint occurrences among data instances and the positive and negative data instances respectively.

Values of Φ close to 1 indicate that the data sequence is in a strong association with the class of interest (e.g. built-up areas). Values close to -1 indicate that the data sequence is strongly related to any class which is not the class of interest. Values of Φ near to zero are related to data sequences close to the point of equilibrium where an equal number of empirical evidences support both the decision to belong or not to the specific class label.

The SML can be a scalable solution for global image data classification scenarios because of reduced computational requirements and reduced input data requirements including both input image data and training data as compared to other classification frameworks. The statistical frequentist theoretical background of the SML method ensures that the best classification decision can be taken even in presence of high noise rates in the learning set, under the weak assumption that the at least half + 1 of training samples are correct. Under this weak majority rule assumption, there is no need for full a priori spatial and temporal alignment between the input imagery and the learning set allowing the SML to be trained from lower resolution categorical data and with data including an expected rate of thematic change up to 50%. In SML classification, input image data calibration can be reduced drastically, since the SML learning process is computationally efficient and can be executed “on-the-fly” for every input satellite scene discovering scene-specific data-class associations. The robustness of the SML to noise related either to scale generalization, spatial displacement and thematic content including temporal mismatch have been demonstrated in a dedicated study on sensitivity analysis by [35].

D. Classification of built-up areas

Although our main purpose is to extract “built-up areas” and then estimate their vertical component, we also classify “Forest/vegetation,” and “Permanent water bodies” as additional landcover classes because of the high risk of confusion with the built-up areas class. This is essentially related to scattering mechanism ambiguities between built-up areas and vegetation in case of oriented buildings and to low cross scattering powers of orthogonal buildings and water which can lead to confusion between these two classes [36].

Two global public datasets are used for training the SML classifier: i) for the “built-up areas” class we used the Global Human Settlement Layer built-up (GHSL) grid derived from Landsat data at 30 m resolution for epoch 2015 [24]; ii) for the “Forest/vegetation,” and “Permanent water bodies”, we used the Copernicus Global Land Cover map for epoch 2015, derived from PROBA-V sensor and available at 100 m spatial resolution [37]. The “built-up areas” class is defined as the area covered by “roofed constructions above ground which are intended or used for the shelter of humans, animals, things, the production of economic goods or the delivery of services” [38]. These targets are characterized in PolSAR data by a strong double-bounce return because of their constituent materials and geometry [31]. The “Forest/Vegetation” class is used to refer to areas of natural vegetation, parks and cropland. In PolSAR, this class is characterized by diffused scattering that does not change significantly with rotation around the radar line of sight. The “Permanent water bodies” class comprises inland water bodies and sea surface water that are characterized by specular or surface reflection depending on the condition of the surface.

Fig 2. Overall workflow for built-up areas extraction and assessment of the vertical component in the context of the Symbolic Machine Learning (SML)- The star symbol * refers to the spatial resolution of the data.

E. Classification of the vertical component of built-up areas

The purpose of this part of the work is to estimate the building height class (BHC) from 5m-resolution satellite data classification, and for three different BHCs: namely, low-rise building (LRB), mid-rise buildings (MRB), and high-rise buildings (HRB). Given the absence of a global consensus on the definition of high-rise buildings and the use of cut-off values ranging between 10 and 30 meters [39], it was decided to use the lower bound value of 10 meters to ensure a wide applicability of the proposed method. Mid-rise buildings usually correspond to residential apartments and commercial buildings which only a few stories up to 2 or three which lower bound would correspond to 6 meters approximately.

The same classification framework building on the SML classifier is also used here. The SML was trained by using the generalized vertical component (GVC) of built-up areas at 250m resolution, as can be extracted from global spaceborne Digital Surface Models available in open scientific domain at the spatial resolution of 30m by spatial filtering and regression techniques [41]. This 250 m resolution of the input training data of the GCV is broader than the input

sensor data. Nevertheless, this scale can be considered still suitable approximating the spatial requirements of specific global modelling exercises requiring information on building height and volume; namely population spatial modelling, the urban Local Climate Zones (LCZ) [40] classification and urban climate models.

An overview of the workflow for built-up areas extraction and assessment of the vertical component is provided in Fig 2. As illustrated in the flow diagram there are 6 output confidence layers organized into two groups: the first group corresponds to the confidence layers describing built-up areas, vegetation and permanent water (described in section II.D), and the second group corresponds to confidence layers describing low-rise, mid-rise and high-rise buildings (described in section II.E).

F. Collection of validation datasets

To assess the effectiveness of the proposed method for built-up areas extraction and estimation of the vertical component we validate the results using single building footprints as a reference dataset. For Chicago, detailed building footprints including information on number of storeys were available from the City of

Chicago³ with a last update in 2015 matching the date of acquisition of PALSAR-2 scene. For Tokyo, the reference data was limited to building footprints without any information on building heights collected during the period 2019-2020 by the Geospatial Information Authority of Japan⁴. All reference data were rasterized to a spatial resolution of 5 meters for the validation of built-up areas detection. For the assessment of the vertical component in Chicago, the validation was performed at a spatial resolution of 250 meters consistent with the spatial resolution of GVC used as a training set in the SML. The number of storeys were grouped into three classes corresponding to:

- Low-rise buildings: floor number ≤ 2
- Mid-rise buildings: $3 \leq$ floor number ≤ 4
- High-rise buildings: floor number ≥ 5

III. RESULTS

A. Classification of built-up areas in Chicago :

The results shown in Fig. 3 (a) represent the Yamaguchi four-component decomposition used to compose full colour images with the following red, green, and blue (RGB) colour coding: red for the double bounce power (P_d), green for the volume scattering power (P_v), and blue for the surface scattering power (P_s). The outputs of the SML are represented in terms of confidence values (ENDI) per pixel for each of the three classes and displayed in a RGB colour image with: ENDI of built-up areas the red band; ENDI of Forest/vegetation in the green band and ENDI of permanent water in the blue band Fig. 3 (b). A visual inspection of the SML outputs shows that built-up areas (red band) are well captured despite the intertwining of built-up features with vegetation in particular in the outskirts of Chicago urban centre. Overall all three classes are well identified, in particular the built-up class. This is mainly related to orthogonal urban layout in Chicago, which is typical to US cities with the main streets following the cardinal directions [42].

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR BUILT-UP CLASSIFICATION IN CHICAGO

<i>True Negatives (TN)</i>	9781492
<i>False Negatives (FN)</i>	308407
<i>True Positives (TP)</i>	2228240
<i>Balanced Accuracy</i>	0.85
<i>Commission Error</i>	0.48
<i>Omission Error</i>	0.12

³ <https://data.cityofchicago.org/Buildings/Building-Footprints-current/-/hz9b-7nh8>

⁴ <https://fgd.gsi.go.jp/download/menu.php>

Fig. 3. (a) PALSAR-2 Four component decomposition in Chicago (b) RGB output of the SML classification. (c) Binary built-up areas derived from the ENDI of built-up areas

To enable the validation of the results against the rasterized building footprints, the ENDI confidence values are binarized by applying the Otsu thresholding technique Fig. 3 (c).

TABLE II shows the statistics associated with the confusion matrix together with the performance metrics, namely the Balanced Accuracy, the Commission and Omission Errors. The Balanced Accuracy defined by [43] has been used to solve the problem of class imbalance (i.e. rare built-up pixels compared to non built-up) by equally weighting the errors within each class (Equation 2).

The Commission Error corresponds to the true positive rate also called user's accuracy while the omission error refers to the true negative rate and is also known as precision or producer's accuracy. The Balanced Accuracy value of 0.85 shows the effectiveness of the proposed classification framework, building on the SML with the four decomposition components as input features, despite using a coarse training dataset (30 meters resolution) for deriving a map of built-up area at 5 meters.

$$\text{Balanced Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Sensitivity} + \text{Specificity}}{2} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{FP + TN} \quad (4)$$

B. Classification of built-up areas in Tokyo from ascending and descending orbits :

The same workflow is tested in Tokyo where both scenes from ascending and descending orbits were available. Fig. 4 shows the outputs of SML for the three classes, displayed in RGB colour images, from the ascending orbit ($ENDI_{asc}$), from the descending orbit ($ENDI_{desc}$) and the maximized ENDI ($ENDI_{max}$) calculated by the combination of the two previous rescaled outputs in the range [0, 1] taking the maximum values of $ENDI_{asc}$ and $ENDI_{desc}$ as follows:

$$ENDI_{max} = ENDI_{asc} \cup ENDI_{desc} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 4. Outputs of SML for the three classes, displayed in RGB colour images: (a) from the ascending orbit, (b) from the descending orbit and (c) the maximized ENDI

Both images from ascending and descending orbits seem to delineate well the built-up areas when classified with the SML. However a closer look at the results shows some underdetections of built-up areas in the ascending scene, in particular in areas dominated by oriented buildings with respect to the radar line of sight. Inversely, in the descending scene, those same areas are well captured as they show an orthogonal direction. This contrasting behavior of the urban targets suggests that a maximization of the ENDI outputs from the ascending and descending orbits would allow recovering the under-detected built-up areas in each individual scene and reduce the confusion with the vegetation and other natural targets.

In order to examine those results quantitatively, we analyze the decomposed power contributions of selected patches corresponding to built-up areas (a and b) and vegetation from (c) the ascending (Fig. 5 (a)) and descending scenes (Fig. 5 (b)). In the ascending scene, patch a is composed of predominantly orthogonal buildings resulting in a prevalence of surface/double-bounce scattering powers (P_s and P_d). Patch b instead, is dominated by oriented buildings which yield to high contribution of volume scattering and to a potential confusion with patch c. The opposite behavior is observed when looking at the results of the decomposed power contributions in the descending scene. In patch a, we observe an increase in the volume scattering. Inversely, in patch b, there is a significant increase of the double bounce and surface scattering at the detriment of volume scattering. While in patch c, the decomposed power contributions are almost constant.

Fig. 5. Color-coded decomposition image of (a) the ascending and (b) descending scenes in Tokyo

The results of the accuracy assessment for built-up areas from the individual scenes and from the maximized ENDI are shown in

TABLE III. All SML outputs were binarized using the Otsu's threshold to calculate the pixel based confusion matrix.

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR BUILT-UP CLASSIFICATION IN TOKYO

	Binary Built-up		
	$ENDI_{asc}$	$ENDI_{desc}$	$ENDI_{max}$
True Negatives	18267661	18189865	17028138
False Negatives	2063307	2303206	1124932
False Positives	3701500	3779296	4941023
True Positives	8165032	7925133	9103407
Balanced Accuracy	0.81	0.80	0.83
Commission Error	0.31	0.32	0.35
Omission Error	0.20	0.22	0.11

The cross-comparison of performances of built-up areas detection with the SML, evidences clear limitations in the capacity to discriminate built-up areas using one single acquisition orbit in complex urban landscapes. Tokyo's urban configuration does not always follow a regular grid pattern. There are deviations from the orthogonal configurations leading to a heterogeneous and complex urban system. In these contexts, the typical ascending scenes can only capture part of this urban complexity. There is a strong added-value in benefiting from complementarity between the ascending and descending orbits to have a full picture of the built-up areas. This was demonstrated by the Balanced Accuracy of 0.83 obtained with the maximized ENDI compared to the ones obtained from the individually processed scenes (0.81 from the ascending and 0.80 from the descending).

This also suggests that the complementarity between the ascending and descending acquisitions can mitigate the problem of underdetection of built-up areas and confusion with vegetated surfaces.

C. Assessment of the vertical component in Chicago :

Using the same classification framework, buildings' vertical component was assessed in Chicago and evaluated with respect to the reference data on number of floors aggregated at a spatial resolution of 250 meters to ensure consistency with the input training data. In Fig. 6(b) the outputs of the SML classifier are represented in a RGB composite with the three identified classes of building heights as follows: ENDI of low-rise buildings in the red band, ENDI of mid-rise buildings in the green band, ENDI of high-

rise buildings in the blue band. These results are obtained at the native spatial resolution of the PALSAR-2 scene which in this case is 5 meters. In comparison, the building heights assessed from the input training data are represented by the GVC which is delivered at a spatial resolution of 250 x 250 meters (Fig. 6(a)). It is interesting to note the correspondence between the patterns of high-rise buildings represented in orange and red colors in the GVC dataset and the spatial distribution of high-rise buildings detected in the PALSAR-2 data. While high-rise buildings are clearly identifiable in the PALSAR-2 scene, mid-rise and low-rise buildings seem to be less distinct.

Fig. 6. Outputs of the SML classifier for the estimation of the vertical component in Chicago. (a) Training data derived from the GVC at 250 meters; (b) RGB composite of ENDI of low-rise buildings in the red band, ENDI of mid-rise buildings in the green band, ENDI of high-rise buildings in the blue band (c) the reference building footprints rasterized at 5 meters and (d) the reference data on number of floors per building.

The results of the performance assessment at 250 meters are represented in terms of Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) per different BHC in TABLE IV. In addition, we report about the Mean Bias Error (MBE) which indicates whether the model overestimates or

underestimates the actual vertical component. These results correspond to a direct comparison of the densities of each BHC in a 250 meters grid cell with the reference BHC densities obtained from the detailed building footprints. The estimated BHC densities were

derived by first rescaling the 5m-res ENDI outputs in the range [0-1], followed by automatic binarization using the Otsu approach, then the aggregation of output binary map at 250 meters using the average operator to obtain continuous values that can be directly compared to the reference densities BHC. The quantitative performance assessment confirms the visual assessment showing that the classification of high-rise buildings results in the lowest RMSE and MBE (MBE close to 0), followed by mid-rise buildings (RMSE of 0.034 and MBE also close to 0). Whereas the classification of low-rise buildings tends to largely overestimate this class of building morphology (MBE = 0.2).

TABLE IV. PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT OF THE CLASSIFICATION OF THE VERTICAL COMPONENT AT 250 METERS PER CATEGORY OF BUILDING MORPHOLOGY

<i>Estimated vertical component (250 m)</i>	RMSE	MBE
<i>Low-rise buildings</i>	0.25	0.2
<i>Mid-rise buildings</i>	0.034	0.02
<i>High-rise buildings</i>	0.032	0.01

Chicago is the birthplace of skyscrapers and home to 1,366 completed high-rises, 48 of which stand taller than 183 m. The fact that the SML applied to the PALSAR-2 data is successful in extracting this category of buildings is encouraging while calling for an adjustment of the height thresholds applied in this work to discriminate low-rise. One approach could be to adopt the Local Climate zones classification of urban systems which distinguishes the classes of building morphology in relation to their physical properties and their impact on urban heat islands [44].

IV. CONCLUSION

This research investigated urban areas information extraction and characterization from PolSAR data using the generic SML classifier. The standard four components' polarimetric power target decomposition proposed by Yamaguchi are used as input feature descriptors to the SML process. The experimental results obtained with PALSAR-2 over two cities with different landscape and characteristics of built-up areas demonstrate that the proposed generic method can achieve three main challenges of urban remote sensing: i) enabling fully automated delineation of built-up areas at a spatial resolution of 5 meters with a balanced accuracy of 85% using global 30m-res land cover data as learning set, ii) assessing the building

height class with a RMSE of 0.25, 0.034, and 0.032 for the low-rise, mid-rise, and high-rise building density class, respectively, and iii) dealing with the scattering components of buildings with different orientation angles by combining data from ascending and descending orbits for enhanced mapping of built-up areas. The performance of the classification schema for both horizontal and vertical built-up areas characterization were obtained through a training of the SML with coarse resolution globally available training data (at 30, 100 and 250 meters) allowing the deployment of the method over large areas and in different types of urban environments. The computation is efficient and fast with less than 5 minutes for the classification of the PALSAR-2 on a workstation with 3.5 GHz Intel Xeon processor equipped with 64 GB of RAM. The single CPU core processing spikes at 50% of RAM.

Further analyses are needed to better distinguish orthogonal and oriented built-up areas from one single scene and one specific orbit. One future area of investigation is the use the novel scattering power factorization framework and the associated roll-invariant parameters for the analysis of PolSAR imagery recently proposed by [16]. Alternatively, it would be interesting to ingest the six-component scattering power model-based decomposition in the SML to account for the compounded dipoles and oriented dipole structures as seen in oriented urban areas, vegetation areas, and sloped surfaces [45]. To solve the issue of overdetection of low-rise buildings, different height thresholds need to be tested in different urban contexts and assessed in terms of generalization capabilities. Finally to better understand the advantages and limitations of the proposed approach, it is desirable to compare it to other classification schemas such as the Wishart maximum likelihood classifier, Support Vector Machines and Random Forests which are considered as the state-of-the-art PolSAR image classification methods [46].

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REFERENCES

- [1] OECD and E. Commission, *Cities in the World*. 2020.

- [2] W. Colglazier, "The Sustainable Development Goals: Roadmaps to Progress," *AAAS Sci. Dipl.*, vol. 7, no. 1, Mar. 2018.
- [3] I. Zambon, A. Colantoni, and L. Salvati, "Horizontal vs vertical growth: Understanding latent patterns of urban expansion in large metropolitan regions," *Sci. Total Environ.*, vol. 654, pp. 778–785, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.11.182.
- [4] P. Gong *et al.*, "Annual maps of global artificial impervious area (GAIA) between 1985 and 2018," *Remote Sens. Environ.*, vol. 236, p. 111510, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.rse.2019.111510.
- [5] T. Chen, A. Sun, and R. Niu, "Effect of Land Cover Fractions on Changes in Surface Urban Heat Islands Using Landsat Time-Series Images," *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, vol. 16, no. 6, p. 971, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.3390/ijerph16060971.
- [6] G. C. Iannelli and P. Gamba, "Urban Extent Extraction Combining Sentinel Data in the Optical and Microwave Range," *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Appl. Earth Obs. Remote Sens.*, vol. 12, no. 7, pp. 2209–2216, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1109/JSTARS.2019.2920678.
- [7] Y. Zhou *et al.*, "A global map of urban extent from nightlights," *Environ. Res. Lett.*, vol. 10, no. 5, p. 054011, May 2015, doi: 10.1088/1748-9326/10/5/054011.
- [8] W. Zhang, W. Li, C. Zhang, and W. B. Ouimet, "Detecting horizontal and vertical urban growth from medium resolution imagery and its relationships with major socioeconomic factors," *Int. J. Remote Sens.*, vol. 38, no. 12, pp. 3704–3734, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.1080/01431161.2017.1302113.
- [9] M. Li, E. Koks, H. Taubenböck, and J. van Vliet, "Continental-scale mapping and analysis of 3D building structure," *Remote Sens. Environ.*, vol. 245, p. 111859, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.rse.2020.111859.
- [10] T. Esch *et al.*, "Breaking new ground in mapping human settlements from space – The Global Urban Footprint," *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.*, vol. 134, pp. 30–42, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2017.10.012.
- [11] D. Wen, X. Huang, A. Zhang, and X. Ke, "Monitoring 3D Building Change and Urban Redevelopment Patterns in Inner City Areas of Chinese Megacities Using Multi-View Satellite Imagery," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 11, no. 7, p. 763, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.3390/rs11070763.
- [12] X. Huang, Y. Cao, and J. Li, "An automatic change detection method for monitoring newly constructed building areas using time-series multi-view high-resolution optical satellite images," *Remote Sens. Environ.*, vol. 244, p. 111802, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.rse.2020.111802.
- [13] Y. La, H. Bagan, and Y. Yamagata, "Urban land cover mapping under the Local Climate Zone scheme using Sentinel-2 and PALSAR-2 data," *Urban Clim.*, vol. 33, p. 100661, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.uclim.2020.100661.
- [14] S. Abdikan and C. Bayik, "Assessment of ALOS PALSAR 25-m mosaic data for land cover mapping," Jun. 2017, pp. 1–4, doi: 10.1109/Multi-Temp.2017.8035251.
- [15] D. Xiang, T. Tang, C. Hu, Q. Fan, and Y. Su, "Built-up Area Extraction from PolSAR Imagery with Model-Based Decomposition and Polarimetric Coherence," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 8, no. 8, p. 685, Aug. 2016, doi: 10.3390/rs8080685.
- [16] D. Ratha, P. Gamba, A. Bhattacharya, and A. C. Frery, "Novel Techniques for Built-Up Area Extraction From Polarimetric SAR Images," *IEEE Geosci. Remote Sens. Lett.*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 177–181, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1109/LGRS.2019.2914913.
- [17] S. De, L. Bruzzone, A. Bhattacharya, F. Bovolo, and S. Chaudhuri, "A Novel Technique Based on Deep Learning and a Synthetic Target Database for Classification of Urban Areas in PolSAR Data," *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Appl. Earth Obs. Remote Sens.*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 154–170, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1109/JSTARS.2017.2752282.
- [18] M. Che, P. Du, and P. Gamba, "2- and 3-D Urban Change Detection With Quad-PolSAR Data," *IEEE Geosci. Remote Sens. Lett.*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 68–72, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1109/LGRS.2017.2773471.
- [19] M. Pesaresi, V. Syrris, and A. Julea, "A New Remote Sensing Data Classification Method Based on Symbolic Machine Learning," <http://dx.doi.org/10.2788/638672>, 2015.
- [20] V. Syrris and M. Pesaresi, "On the Assessment of Automatically Processing HR/VHR Imagery Using Low-Resolution Global Reference Data," presented at the Joint Urban Remote Sensing Event, Apr. 2013.
- [21] L. Gueguen and M. Pesaresi, "Interscale learning and classification for global HR/VHR image information extraction," in *2014 IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, 2014, pp. 1481–1484.

- [22] M. Pesaresi, "Global Fine-Scale Information Layers: the Need of a Paradigm Shift," in *Conference on Big Data from Space (BiDS'14)*, 2014.
- [23] C. Corbane *et al.*, "Application of the Symbolic Machine Learning to Copernicus VHR Imagery: The European Settlement Map," *IEEE Geosci. Remote Sens. Lett.*, vol. 17, no. 7, pp. 1153–1157, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1109/LGRS.2019.2942131.
- [24] C. Corbane *et al.*, "Automated global delineation of human settlements from 40 years of Landsat satellite data archives," *Big Earth Data*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 140–169, 2019.
- [25] C. Corbane *et al.*, "Big earth data analytics on Sentinel-1 and Landsat imagery in support to global human settlements mapping," *Big Earth Data*, vol. 1, no. 1–2, pp. 118–144, 2017, doi: 10.1080/20964471.2017.1397899.
- [26] M. Pesaresi, C. Corbane, A. Julea, A. Florczyk, V. Syrris, and P. Soille, "Assessment of the Added-Value of Sentinel-2 for Detecting Built-up Areas," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 8, no. 4, p. 299, Apr. 2016, doi: 10.3390/rs8040299.
- [27] C. Corbane *et al.*, "Automatic Image Data Analytics from a Global Sentinel-2 Composite for the Study of Human Settlements," presented at the Big Data from Space (BiDS'19), 2019, doi: 10.2760/848593.
- [28] C. Corbane *et al.*, "Enhanced automatic detection of human settlements using Sentinel-1 interferometric coherence," *Int. J. Remote Sens.*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 842–853, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.1080/01431161.2017.1392642.
- [29] European Commission, Joint Research Centre, *Atlas of the Human Planet 2018, a World of Cities*. Publications Office of the European Union, 2018.
- [30] A. Shakibamanesh and B. Ebrahimi, "Toward Practical Criteria for Analyzing and Designing Urban Blocks," in *Sustainability in Urban Planning and Design [Working Title]*, IntechOpen, 2020.
- [31] J.-S. Lee and E. Pottier, *Polarimetric radar imaging: from basics to applications*. Boca Raton: CRC Press, 2009.
- [32] B. Azmedroub, M. Ouarzeddine, and B. Souissi, "Extraction of Urban Areas From Polarimetric SAR Imagery," *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Appl. Earth Obs. Remote Sens.*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 2583–2591, Jun. 2016, doi: 10.1109/JSTARS.2016.2527242.
- [33] Y. Yamaguchi, A. Sato, W.-M. Boerner, R. Sato, and H. Yamada, "Four-Component Scattering Power Decomposition With Rotation of Coherency Matrix," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 49, no. 6, pp. 2251–2258, Jun. 2011, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2010.2099124.
- [34] Feng Xu and Ya-Qiu Jin, "Deorientation theory of polarimetric scattering targets and application to terrain surface classification," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 43, no. 10, pp. 2351–2364, Oct. 2005, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2005.855064.
- [35] M. Pesaresi, V. Syrris, and A. Julea, "Benchmarking of the Symbolic Machine Learning classifier with state of the art image classification methods - application to remote sensing imagery, EUR 27518," Publications Office of the European Union, JRC Technical Report EUR 27518, 2015. [Online]. Available: doi:10.2788/638672.
- [36] D. Xiang, *Urban Area Information Extraction From Polarimetric SAR Data*. Stockholm: KTH Royal Institute of Technology, 2016.
- [37] Marcel Buchhorn *et al.*, "Copernicus Global Land Service: Land Cover 100m: epoch 2015: Globe." Zenodo, Oct. 01, 2019, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3243509.
- [38] M. Pesaresi *et al.*, "A Global Human Settlement Layer From Optical HR/VHR RS Data: Concept and First Results," *Sel. Top. Appl. Earth Obs. Remote Sens. IEEE J. Of*, vol. 6, pp. 2102–2131, 2013.
- [39] G. Craighead, *High-rise security and fire life safety*, 3rd ed. Amsterdam ; Boston: Butterworth-Heinemann/Elsevier, 2009.
- [40] B. Bechtel *et al.*, "Towards consistent mapping of urban structure-global human settlement layer and local climate zones," *ISPRS-Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spat. Inf. Sci.*, vol. 41, pp. 1371–1378, 2016.
- [41] M. Pesaresi, C. Corbane, P. Politis, R. Chao, and E. Ng, "Study on the estimation of generalized vertical components of built-up areas through processing of global spaceborne Digital Elevation Models," *PLoS ONE*, in press.
- [42] D. R. Goldfield, Ed., *Encyclopedia of American urban history*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications, 2007.
- [43] K. H. Brodersen, O. Cheng Soon, K. E. Stephan, and J. M. Buhmann, "The Balanced Accuracy and Its Posterior Distribution," Aug. 2010, pp. 3121–3124, doi: 10.1109/icpr.2010.764.
- [44] I. D. Stewart and T. R. Oke, "Local Climate Zones for Urban Temperature Studies," *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.*, vol. 93, no. 12, pp. 1879–

- 1900, Dec. 2012, doi: 10.1175/BAMS-D-11-00019.1.
- [45] G. Singh and Y. Yamaguchi, "Model-Based Six-Component Scattering Matrix Power Decomposition," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 56, no. 10, pp. 5687–5704, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2018.2824322.
- [46] P. Du, A. Samat, B. Waske, S. Liu, and Z. Li, "Random Forest and Rotation Forest for fully polarized SAR image classification using polarimetric and spatial features," *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.*, vol. 105, pp. 38–53, Jul. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2015.03.002.